

Technological Andragogy for Teaching ‘The Merchant of Venice’

Dr Nagraj Dasmayya Kharade

Assistant Professor, Shri Omkarnath Malpani Law College Sangamner, Ahilyanagar- 422605.
(Affiliated to Savitribai Phule Pune University, Pune.)

Dr. Kapil Kulkarni

J. S. M. College Alibaug, Raigad (Affiliated to Mumbai University, Mumbai.)

Abstract

The students pursuing five-year program in law are expected to study different forms of literature including drama, short stories, poems and their relevance to the field of law in a course, Law and Literature. It is a challenging task for the teachers to deal with the students as they hardly have any interest in studying and understanding the literature. It is of utmost importance to make them aware about the role of literature in understanding the law using different teaching aids. Along with the conventional mode of teaching, modern technological pedagogy would serve the desired expectations. This research paper attempts to explore and amplify the technological tools which can be used to create interest about literature among the students while teaching the play Merchant of Venice by Shakespeare, resulting in the effective teaching and learning process.

Keywords: Law, Literature, Technology, Pedagogy, Teaching-Learning, etc.

Introduction

It is often considered that Law and Literature are irrelevant as they belong to different fields and related to different classes of people. In fact, Law and Literature are not novel fields. They have a diverse and dynamic relationship (Sharma, 2021). Introducing literary texts in legal education helps law students in many ways. Firstly, it helps to shape their interpretative skills and understand legal issues and the complexities of law. Literature provides the students insights about law by offering diverse scenarios reflected in novels, dramas, short stories etc. dealing with legal concepts. The students of law, especially those who are pursuing BA LLB, a five-year program in law, have a course entitled Law and Literature, are meant to study the play The Merchant of Venice. These students have least interest in studying and understanding the literature. However, the conventional mode of teaching using chalk and board, would be a failure in teaching- learning process. In order to bring interest among the students, a blend of conventional and modern teaching methods must be incorporated. In the world of technology, Gen Z should be taught by integrating technological tools to make it more effective.

The phrase “Information and Communication Technology,” abbreviated as “ICT,” refers to the use of different types of technology to the management, processing, and transmission of information, as well as the facilitation of communication (Ratheeswari, 2018). The

technology has revolutionized teaching- learning process by making the learning more engaging, interactive, flexible and accessible. Making use of technology in teaching of literature in the context of legal education would encourage students to create interest by introducing innovative techniques to study. Students can experience real life learning by watching movies, power-point presentations, etc. This research paper studies how the play Merchant of Venice can be taught by employing technology as the best pedagogy. It will also examine the usefulness of technology in making them take keen interest in literature, involve in interactive sessions and think about literature through legal lens.

Integrating Technological tools in Teaching 'The Merchant of Venice (1999)'

The play Merchant of Venice by William Shakespeare is a part of legal education. Law students should study the literature from legal perspective and understand the legal complex issues through literature, is the motive behind this. The first scene of the fourth act deals with the courtroom trial scene that takes place in court of the Duke of Venice, is significant for law students to study as it is related to law. The scene focuses on the importance of drafting, Portia twists the story, asking Shylock take the pound of flesh of Antonio as per the bond, but without spilling a single drop of blood. It is a crucial aspect for the students of law. Merely narrating the story of the play, discussing the themes, explaining the characters, following the traditional method of teaching would make the technology driven students passive and the learning becomes ineffective. Therefore, there is an immense need for teachers to mould themselves as per needs and learning interests of the students.

In the technological era, the world full of information and communication technology (ICT), the teachers have to adopt technology and become Techno savvy. The students are getting more interested in learning with technology (Roy, 2019, p. 356) so the focus of the teachers should be on teaching with technology. In order to teach any topic, the teachers are required to use technological tools from email, the earlier forms of online communication to Instagram, the latest and favourite social media platform of youth, must be integrated. Technology has digitized classrooms through digital learning tools like computers, iPads, smartphones and smart digital whiteboards. (Roy, 2019, p. 356) The play Merchant of Venice can be taught different technological tools like audio-visual aids, PPTs, MOOCs, etc. through projectors, whiteboards, smartphones, etc.

PowerPoint Presentations

The classrooms are fully equipped with digital facilities including smart board and LCD projectors, so PowerPoint presentations (PPTs) are the best options to get started using technology for teaching the play. PowerPoint Presentations would be a powerful tool to understand the complex ideas in simple ways. The teachers can create PPTs on the play covering general information about the play, introduction of characters, themes, a brief

summary etc. Major themes of the play such as friendship, justice, religious conflict, etc. can be highlighted using bullets point to convey them with proper emphasis. An effective PPT using different images, clip arts, emojis, colourful slides can attract students' attention and help them to get familiar with important elements of the play. An advance teacher can make good use of animations and flowcharts to demonstrate the sequence of the incidents taken place in the play. Adding proper images of the places like Venice and Belmont, characters like Antonio, Bassanio, Portia and Shylock, caskets, and courtroom scene can create an immersive experience. Finally, some questions and quizzes can be conducted based on the play to make it more interactive and engaging. Using Artificial Intelligence (AI) tools, especially Gamma AI and Slides AI, teachers can create effective PPTs and use them in classroom teaching.

Audio-Visual Aids

Audio-visual aid is a part of multimodal learning which is considered as the best option for effective learning. It engages students in multiple ways such as watching, listening, reading and thinking. Audio-visual aids include movies, dramas, short skits, reels, vlogs, YouTube videos, Animated videos or any recording related to the teaching material. YouTube and other platforms provide videos related to teaching. The play Merchant of Venice has given rise to different videos along with a movie. Movision Entertainment and Arlight Films have produced 2 hours and 11 mins duration film adaptation of the play The Merchant of Venice. The film is available on YouTube and the link is <https://youtu.be/crNWgsdqP9g?si=WywDqHjBbvFkmRVR>. The teachers can download the movie and it can be shown to the students on a big screen with proper audio system to give them a theatre like feel.

This highly effective teaching strategy will not only make the students involve in the play but also relate the story with their own life. The students can grasp and comprehend the entire courtroom trail scene, the dialogues of the major characters, the flesh taking effort of Shylock and the twist followed by it, can be witnessed properly. The students can imagine a real courtroom trail scene and analyze the scene from different angles. Once the film is shown, a question-answer session can be conducted to check whether the students understood the play or not. This approach of education and entertainment (edutainment) will surely create a keen interest among the students about the play and literature at large.

Video Lectures

Using Video Lectures for teaching is another beneficial tool. The students can access the video lectures any time, get engaged with the video and they can understand the play in a better way. Teaching Drama through available resources on internet is a good idea but going beyond it and creating our educational videos is the best one. Creating video lectures has the following benefits. First of all, it helps working-students by bridging the gap given by

their absence during regular lectures, secondly it supports regular students by giving them the opportunity to recover lectures lost due to forced or elective absence, thirdly, it assists students having difficulties with the lecture's spoken language and finally it also gives students a mean to review critical sections and check their notes. (Ronchetti, 2010) Therefore, creating our own video lecture on the play *The Merchant of Venice* would be a great idea to make the teaching of drama worthy. Teachers can create video lectures covering the characters, plot, themes and major elements of the play and upload the same on YouTube, followed by sharing its link with the students. The traditional learning model based on frontal lectures held in class corresponds generally to a passive student approach, and as such it has been highly criticized. (Ronchetti, 2010, p. 45) The benefactor can also recite the dialogues of the play to make the video more interesting, so that students and other lovers of literature can also get benefitted. Teachers can use different software like Movavi Video Editor, Camtasia, Inshot, Kinemaster, etc. to make effective videos lectures on the play and other topics as well.

Audiobooks and Podcasts

Nowadays students have become lethargic in reading in the digital era because of smart phones and social media networks, so they won't be interested in reading the actual drama. They find it a tedious task and further, the archaic language of Shakespeare will discourage them from reading. As a result, this will affect the teaching and learning of play. In this regard, Audiobooks based on the play, available on internet platforms can be the best solution. Listening to Audios with headsets and isolation from external noises, is one more reason to become fond of audio books (Alcantud-Díaz & Gregori-Signes, 2021). Students can listen act-wise audios of all the five acts of the play '*The Merchant of Venice*' on the given link https://archive.org/details/merchant_of_venice_1005_librivox. Learners can listen these audios whenever they have leisure time and absorb the story with full of attention. Through the dialogues of the courtroom trial scene, particularly the plea for mercy by Portia, the voice modulation of the characters, the learners can also realize the seriousness and gravity of the case and the scene. As learners have lost of interest in listening and watching, this practice would help to recreate interest not in reading literature but listening literature.

Artificial Intelligence/ChatGPT

The classroom scene with teachers standing in front of the board with chalk and duster, imparting knowledge, explaining a topic in monotonous way, is replaced with a techno savvy teacher using multimodal methods to teach a topic, using PPT and audio-visual aids, asking learners to use their android phones, assigning some learning tasks, and encouraging them for experiential learning. In tech-friendly world, teachers are supposed to use and let students use technology for the sake of learning. One such revolutionary technological tool is artificial intelligent or ChatGPT, changing the education system. ChatGPT can provide

direct responses because they have been programmed with a specific set of information and rules for generating responses. (Opara, Adalikwu, & Tolorunleke, 2023, p. 38). Teachers can use ChatGPT meticulously to make the teaching learning activity based resulting in an engaging learning. ChatGPT and other AI tools can be used to teach the play *The Merchant of Venice* in an extra-ordinary way. Teachers can ask students to perform some tasks.

i. Simplify character dialogues from the play using ChatGPT, where students can think of some dialogues of Portia, Shylock, Antonio or Bassanio and convert them in modern English for better understanding.

ii. Prepare a role Play: Taking help of the AI tool, students can prepare a role play and enact accordingly.

iii. Asking questions or doubts: If learners have any doubt about the play, they can ask such questions to ChatGPT.

iv. Creating PPTs: Using ChatGPT and other AI tools, learners can be asked to create PPTs for seminars and presentation.

v. Preparing for exams: Students can be advised to ask ChatGPT the possible questions based on the play for preparing for the exams, including the relationship between the play and legal field.

The students will enjoy performing these tasks and take interest in learning. A Tedious teaching can be turned into outcome-based learning using AI tools effectively. The innovative teaching methods assist the teachers in the teaching of the play and make the teaching-learning process a gratifying activity for both the teachers and students. (Ganpule, 2018, p. 103)

Conclusion

In conclusion, teaching various literary genres to the students pursuing legal education can be a difficult task but not an unattainable one. Teachers can adapt different methods of teaching to make the learning more interesting. They can switch themselves from the traditional method of teaching to the technological method and from teacher-centric to student-centric. This paper focuses on amplifying technological tools in teaching the play *The Merchant of Venice* to enhance the engagement of technology-inclined students in the learning process. The innovative approach of Integrating technology would meet the expectations of the learners through accessibility, flexibility, and clarity. The students can comprehend legal aspects, legal complex issues mentioned in the play and the significance of studying literature in understanding the law.

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